

WIRELESS WORLD RESEARCH FORUM

10.5281/zenodo.14159668

Meeting 49

March 28th-30th 2023

Poznan, Poland

Towards sustainable and automated
communication networks

tietoEVRY

FIMEDO
LABS

Conference in numbers

- **3** days
- **12** technical sessions
- **2** discussion panels
- Around **60** registrants
- **120** registrations for the online panel

Organizers

Our sponsors

Location of Poznań

Poznań:

- **550000** inhabitants (1 mio agglomeration)
- **1000** years-old city
- commercial, industrial and academic center
- more than **10** schools on the university level

Introducing Poznań

Faculty of Electronics and Telecommunications

Reason #1

Poznan, the first capital city of Poland

Old Town - Marketsquare

Reason #2

Great touristic city

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Great touristic city

Reason #3

Great science

Strong mathematicians:

Marian Rejewski, Henryk Zygalski, Jerzy Różycki

Enigma encryption machine encryption code breakers!

Prof. Władysław Orlicz

advances in mathematical topology – **Orlicz spaces**

Reason #4

Goats' show

Reason #5

Food delights

One will find new flavour of potatoes!

POZNANSKA
PYRA

**We wish you fruitful time
at the 49th WWRF in Poznań**

